

MODELS AND ALGORITHMS OF PROCESS MANAGEMENT MODERN DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN EDUCATION

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Abstract: This article discusses the most important problem of the development of the modern education system – the use of digital technologies in the educational process. The authors of the article characterize the concept of digital technologies, highlight the advantages of their use in the learning process, analyze the process of digital transformation of education.

Keywords: educational process, personalization of the learning process, technological platforms, digital transformation of education, digital technologies.

A key trend in the modern realities of the development of the education system is the introduction of modern digital technologies into the learning process. Digital educational technologies are an essential element that is needed directly to ensure the modern learning process. Educational organizations use modern technological platforms to implement the flow of knowledge, allowing all participants in the learning process to optimally interact using synchronous and asynchronous communication. With the correct organization of the learning process using modern digital technologies, the advantages of this innovation are obvious [1].

They can be represented as follows:

- Minimizing existing technological gaps;
- digital technologies make it possible to effectively solve modern learning problems;
- Personalization of the educational trajectory;
- It becomes possible to erase the boundaries of time and space.

The use of modern digital technologies makes it possible to organize the learning process regardless of the location of the teacher and students: training can be anywhere, at any time. The location of the teacher and students is no longer so important, it is enough to have a "guide" to the world of knowledge [3]. Digital technologies help the teacher to optimally control the educational activities of students. It should also be noted that the range of possible actions of the subjects of the educational process is increasing, while their responsibility for achieving high educational results is growing. The widespread use of multimedia educational materials, which are developed taking into account the requirements of pedagogical design, largely removes from teachers the responsibility for "delivering educational content", allowing them to focus on pedagogical support for students, educational and organizational and pedagogical work.

Modern digital technologies are being updated and distributed fairly quickly. This opens up unlimited access to digital tools, materials and services. Students and teachers gain unprecedented control over their information space and its joint application. Their opportunities for self-control and mutual control, for the formation of interest in learning, for meaningful learning have expanded [4, 5].

Figure 1. Algorithm of the first kind when setting the problem

Thus, the basis for the use of modern digital technologies in education is created by the unfolding new stage of the digital revolution, which makes digital technologies a reliable, publicly available method for solving the tasks set. The essence of the digital transformation of education is the movement towards personalization of the learning process based on the use of modern digital technologies. Its key feature is that digital

technologies help to actually apply completely new pedagogical practices, as well as models for organizing the educational process.

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